

1 **Mapping conservation priorities across benthic and pelagic environments provides**
2 **actionable management insights: the Bay of Biscay case study**

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10 **Abstract**

11 Effective marine conservation requires robust spatially explicit approaches to translate complex
12 data into actionable insights that inform management. We developed a multi-zone spatial
13 prioritisation method to identify conservation priority areas across benthic and pelagic
14 environments under multiple scenarios with varying objectives and constraints. These
15 prioritisation scenarios, combined with further evaluation of important areas for key targeted
16 ecological features and quantification of potential socioeconomic impacts (here, on fisheries),
17 provided actionable management insights in the Bay of Biscay, where the approach was tested.
18 Compared to a uniform one-zone approach, the multi-zone method enhanced spatial specificity
19 without increasing the conservation footprint. While 30% protection scenario met benthic
20 biodiversity targets, wide-ranging pelagic species like cetaceans were underrepresented,
21 highlighting a need for dynamic management tools. Further mapping of key areas for features
22 such as cetaceans, seabirds, vulnerable ecosystems, and spawning areas provided additional
23 information for targeted management. A substantial portion of current fishing intensity
24 occurred within marine protected areas (MPAs) lacking management plans, emphasising the
25 urgency of implementing effective governance to reconcile conservation and fisheries
26 objectives. Our findings offer practical guidance for designing spatially and thematically
27 differentiated strategies to build an ecologically representative and operationally effective MPA
28 network and inform broader marine spatial planning in the Bay of Biscay, while the approach
29 developed here is broadly applicable in other geographical areas.

30 **Keywords:** marine spatial planning, marine protected area, marine conservation, systematic
31 conservation planning, spatial conservation prioritisation

34 1. INTRODUCTION

35 Amid growing anthropogenic pressures, spatial protection has become a key strategy to curb
36 biodiversity loss. Area-based management tools like marine protected areas (MPAs) are widely
37 recognised as vital for conserving ocean biodiversity and maintaining ecosystem functions
38 (Halpern et al., 2010; Lubchenco & Grorud-Colvert, 2015). Global and regional frameworks,
39 such as Target 3 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022) and
40 the European Union (EU) Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (EC, 2020), call for protecting 30%
41 of the ocean by 2030. These frameworks have mobilised conservation efforts, although the
42 emphasis on areal coverage targets has long been debated, with concerns about their scientific
43 basis and practical effectiveness (Kriegl et al., 2021; O’Leary et al., 2016). It is recognised that
44 coverage alone, without effective management (including enforcement) of MPAs and
45 surrounding areas, is insufficient (e.g., Hilborn, 2016; Pendleton et al., 2018).

46 MPAs have now reached 8.4% of global ocean coverage (UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2024) and
47 12.3% of the EU waters (Robuchon et al., 2025). Many of these areas, however, remain
48 unimplemented (*sensu* Grorud-Colvert et al., 2021) or permit high-impact activities that
49 compromise conservation goals (Dureuil et al., 2018; Pike et al., 2024). In the EU, over 85% of
50 MPA coverage falls under protection regimes considered inadequate for biodiversity
51 conservation (Aminian-Biquet et al., 2024). For many of these areas, management plans are
52 still pending. This underscores the need for stronger political commitment and robust spatial
53 planning methods to support effective biodiversity conservation.

54 Spatial conservation prioritisation (SCP) offers a rigorous framework for designing efficient
55 and ecologically representative MPA networks (Moilanen et al., 2009). It enables conservation
56 decision-making to move beyond single-species criteria by allowing for systematic integration
57 of multiple ecological features, which can represent broader ecological dimensions like biotic
58 and abiotic processes and functions (Esteban-Cantillo et al., 2025; Van der Biest et al., 2020).
59 Incorporating these elements is increasingly recognised as essential for restoring and sustaining
60 ecosystem health and resilience (Baskett et al., 2007; Bennett et al., 2009; Lindegren et al.,
61 2018). Conceptual frameworks such as those underpinning the identification processes for Key
62 Biodiversity Areas (IUCN, 2016) and Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas
63 (EBSAs; CBD, 2008) support this shift by enabling an ecosystem-level analysis focused on
64 functional areas and processes rather than individual species or habitats (Clark et al., 2014;
65 Dunn et al., 2025; Lukyanova et al., 2025b).

66 Traditional SCP approaches often overlook a key feature of marine ecosystems that sets them
67 apart from terrestrial ones: their three-dimensional and dynamic nature. Effective planning
68 needs to account for depth and the distinct, yet interconnected, pelagic (water column) and
69 benthic (seabed) environments (Baustian et al., 2014; Brito-Morales et al., 2022; Levin et al.,
70 2018). Benthic features tend to be static or range-limited, whereas pelagic systems are highly
71 dynamic, hosting migratory and wide-ranging species (Esteban-Cantillo et al., 2025; Grantham
72 et al., 2011; Sequeira et al., 2025). Consequently, these environments face different stressors
73 and often require distinct management approaches (e.g., Letessier et al., 2024). Explicitly
74 distinguishing between these environments enables more accurate ecological representation and
75 informs targeted management.

76 SCP is a flexible tool that allows for tackling nuanced conservation problems by supporting,
77 for example, the development of multiple scenarios with varied quantitative targets and
78 constraints (Giakoumi et al., 2025). Thus, the prioritisation process itself can be configured to
79 incorporate management zoning that accounts for the specific protection needs, moving beyond
80 identifying uniform priority sites. Besides, the planning objectives can extend beyond simple
81 spatial coverage to include specific quantified protection targets for each ecological feature of
82 interest. This provides a robust basis for evaluating alternative MPA spatial configurations and
83 their zoning, ensuring balanced ecological representation and directly informing management
84 plans for both new and existing MPAs.

85 Lastly, spatial planning inevitably involves trade-offs, as management measures designed to
86 achieve conservation targets often restrict human activities. To balance marine ecological and
87 socio-economic needs effectively, it is vital to identify and quantify the overlap between
88 conservation priority areas and key human uses, most commonly fisheries (Lubchenco et al.,
89 2003), but also shipping, renewables, and other sectors. This is essential to anticipate conflicts,
90 assess feasibility, and balance ecological goals with socio-economic needs.

91 Against this backdrop, the Bay of Biscay presents a compelling case study. Located in the
92 northeast Atlantic (Figure 1), it is a region of significant ecological and governance complexity.
93 It supports a highly productive, complex ecosystem that hosts important habitats and protected
94 species, as well as extensive fisheries (Borja et al., 2019; ICES, 2021). Falling within French
95 and Spanish exclusive economic zones (EEZs), marine conservation in the Bay is governed by
96 the EU Birds (Directive 2009/147/EC) and Habitats Directives (Directive 92/43/EEC)
97 establishing the Natura 2000 network, national laws, and the OSPAR Convention management

98 mechanisms. Certain areas are also closed to bottom-contact gear under the EU Regulation
99 2019/1241 to protect vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs). This layered legal framework has
100 produced a heterogeneous MPA network, with unclear implementation levels, variable
101 management, and uncertain ecological representativeness. A systematic, spatially explicit
102 assessment is needed to identify gaps and to support conservation and biodiversity-inclusive
103 ecosystem-based marine spatial planning (MSP) in the region (Galparsoro et al., 2025;
104 UNESCO-IOC & European Commission, 2025).

105 Guided by these imperatives, the overarching goal of this study was to identify ecologically
106 representative conservation priority areas, adopting the Bay of Biscay as a case study, and to
107 explore their potential management strategies. The specific objectives were: (i) assess the
108 current state of marine protection by evaluating the spatial coverage and management
109 implementation of existing MPAs; (ii) identify conservation priority areas using a multi-zone
110 planning approach that distinguishes benthic and pelagic environments, and pinpoint areas of
111 importance for specific conservation feature groups to inform management actions; (iii)
112 evaluate alternative planning scenarios and assess whether the 30% protection target ensures
113 comprehensive biodiversity representation of the region; and (iv) analyse potential
114 socioeconomic impacts by quantifying the spatial overlap between conservation priority areas
115 and current fishing activity.

116 **2. METHODS**

117 **2.1. Study area**

118 The study area was delineated based on the combination of biogeographic and management
119 criteria – specifically, the Bay of Biscay’s biogeographic limits (Figure 1) and MSP units in
120 Spain (Real Decreto 150/2023) and France (Arrêté interpréfectoral 2022-073) – to ensure
121 ecological coherence and alignment with existing administrative boundaries. A two-kilometre
122 inland buffer was included to capture coastal features like seabird colonies. Planning units were
123 based on the 10×10 km European Environment Agency grid (EEA, 2023), yielding 5,452 equal-
124 sized squares covering 545,200 km².

125 **2.2. Classification of the currently declared MPAs**

126 Using the EEA Natura 2000 database (version end 2023, EEA & EC (2025)) and OSPAR MPA
127 database (OSPAR, 2025), we categorised each area: (1) based on their primary conservation
128 focus, with targeted species or habitats belonging to Pelagic & Seabirds, Benthic & Demersal,

129 or both (Combined) (Supplementary Materials 1 (SM1), Table A); (2) by their implementation
130 status, differentiating those with existing management plan ('Y' or 'yes' in the databases) and
131 those without (EEA & EC, 2025; OSPAR, 2025; WWF, 2025). VME closures were classified
132 as Benthic & Demersal and as having management plans.

133 **2.3. Ecological features and conservation targets**

134 We revised and expanded the dataset compiled by Lukyanova et al. (2025b) using EBSA
135 criteria. Our conservation features were classified in four broad categories (Table 1):
136 Ecosystems and habitats (N = 65; 7 known VMEs, 12 VME indicators, 15 benthic or coastal
137 habitats, 27 EUSeaMap broad-scale classes of seabed habitats (EUSeaMap habitats), and 4
138 geomorphological features); Species (N = 33; 16 seabirds, 9 cetaceans, 8 fishes); Special
139 importance for life-history stages of species (N = 47; 36 seabirds, 1 cetacean, 10 fishes); and
140 Biodiversity and productivity (N = 6; Table 1). Features were grouped into Pelagic & Seabirds
141 (N = 83) and Benthic & Demersal (N = 68) to allow for planning across these marine
142 environments. The dataset overview is provided in Table 1, with a detailed list in SM1 (Table
143 B) and data processing descriptions in SM2.

144 Following Harris & Holness (2023), we developed heuristic rules to define ecological
145 conservation targets (expressed as percentages of the extent or abundance) based on literature,
146 legislation, extent, data certainty, Red List status, level of occurrence, and science-based expert
147 judgement (Table 1; all targets in SM1). Higher targets were set for features with greater
148 vulnerability, functional importance, rarity, or relevance to life-history stages, in line with
149 Carwardine et al. (2009) and Harris & Holness (2023).

150 Targets for VMEs, benthic and coastal habitats, and geomorphological features were set
151 following Morato et al. (2020) and EU guidelines (European Topic Centre on Biological
152 Diversity, 2010; Giakoumi et al., 2013). For EUSeaMap habitats (predicted distribution of
153 benthic habitat types defined by the EU's Marine Strategy Framework Directive; Vasquez et
154 al., 2023), targets were scaled to habitat extent to avoid overrepresentation of widespread, low-
155 resolution, and high-uncertainty classes (e.g., lower abyssal sediment covers 23% of the area).

156 Species targets were based on EU Red List status and local occurrence, i.e., a base target of
157 20% was applied to 'least concern' and 'abundant' species, increasing with threat level and
158 rarity, reaching 90% for 'critically endangered' and 'rare' species (Bas Gómez, 2023;
159 García-Barón et al., 2021).

160 Among the features of special importance for life-history stages, targets for juvenile
161 distributions were set similarly to species targets but received a higher base target of 30% to
162 reflect the importance of nursery and recruitment areas. Spawning areas for commercial fish,
163 derived from daily egg production surveys, received targets based on expert assessment of the
164 Bay's importance to each stock (SM2, Section 1.1.10). Breeding sites (e.g., seabird colonies,
165 cetacean reproduction areas) received 100% targets. Seabird foraging ranges were assigned a
166 20% base target (Grantham et al., 2011), reduced for extensive ranges to avoid compromising
167 the efficiency of the result (Harris & Holness, 2023).

168 Finally, layers representing overall biodiversity and productivity (i.e. species/habitat richness
169 and productivity) were assigned a 20% base target (Harris et al., 2019; Holness et al., 2014).
170 More spatially restricted areas of high local productivity caused by seamounts, shelf edges, and
171 canyons received higher targets (Fernandez-Arcaya et al., 2017; Grantham et al., 2011).

172 **2.4. Spatial conservation prioritisation scenarios**

173 We examined eight SCP scenarios, all using the same conservation features and targets (Table
174 1, SM1) but differing in objectives, cost layers, and treatment of existing MPAs (Figure 2).
175 Scenarios were grouped by objective: (1) scenarios A-D aimed to protect 30% of the study area
176 (aligned with EU Biodiversity Strategy), maximising conservation benefits, i.e., maximum
177 achievement of the targets, but allowing for shortfall; (2) scenarios E-H aimed to achieve all
178 conservation targets ('Ecological targets'). Within each group, two parameters were varied: (1)
179 Cost layer, i.e., the value against which the planning units were selected (area for A, C, E and
180 G; fishing intensity for B, D, F and H); (2) MPAs inclusion as locked-in, i.e., mandatorily
181 selected, planning units (only MPAs with management plans for A-B and E-F; all existing
182 MPAs for C-D and G-H).

183 All SCP scenarios were formulated as three-zone problems (Figure 3): (1) Pelagic & Seabird,
184 indicating the need for water column and seabird conservation; (2) Benthic & Demersal,
185 reflecting seabed management requirements; and (3) Combined, integrating both environments
186 to achieve conservation targets. A planning unit contributed to a feature's conservation target if
187 selected in its corresponding zone or in the Combined zone. Existing MPAs were mandatorily
188 selected in the zone matching their designated category.

189 We used two cost layers to explore their influence on priority areas selection (Figure 2). They
190 were defined separately for Pelagic & Seabird and Benthic & Demersal zones (Figure 3), and

191 in the Combined zone, representing an overlap of the other two zones, the cost was equal to the
192 sum of their respective costs. The first approach used uniform area-based costs, assigning equal
193 costs to each planning unit. Thereby, the solutions sought to achieve conservation targets within
194 the minimum area, prioritised based solely on ecological value. The second approach
195 incorporated fishing intensity as a cost layer to evaluate how avoiding heavily fished areas
196 altered spatial prioritisation. This cost layer was derived from average annual fishing intensity
197 (2015-2022) by gear type for vessels > 12 m having vessel monitoring systems (EMODnet,
198 2025). For the Pelagic & Seabird zone, we summed intensity by pelagic trawls, seines, and
199 static gears; for the Benthic & Demersal zone, by bottom otter and beam trawls, bottom seines,
200 dredges; for the Combined zone, by all gear types (SM2, Figure S1).

201 To evaluate the added value of the three-zone structure, we also ran all eight scenarios without
202 differentiating between Pelagic and Benthic environments. All prioritisation analyses were
203 conducted in R using *prioritizr* package (Hanson et al., 2022, 2025) with Gurobi solver at a 1%
204 optimality gap (see SM3 for technical details and scripts).

205 **2.5. Determining high-priority areas and quantifying target achievement**

206 To assess the spatial distribution of ecological importance and identify high-priority areas, we
207 conducted a priority ranking of the planning units using an incremental optimisation process.
208 This involved running an additional SCP scenario similar to scenario E (using ecological targets
209 and area-based costs), but without including MPAs as locked-in areas. The analysis was
210 performed by progressively increasing the area to be selected in 2% increments across multiple
211 runs, starting at 0.1% of the study area and continuing until all targets were met. By evaluating
212 overlap of selected planning units across successive runs, we identified consistently chosen
213 ones as crucial for conservation objectives, ranking them higher as priority locations for
214 management actions. Furthermore, this iterative process enabled us to quantify the percentage
215 of each conservation target achieved at any given level of area protection coverage (e.g., 10%,
216 30%, or 50%).

217 **2.6. Pinpointing priority areas for specific conservation features**

218 To generate more specific and actionable insights for conservation and management, we
219 assessed the spatial distribution of ecological importance across several feature groups to
220 pinpoint the most critical zones within the identified priority areas in Scenario G (incorporating
221 all existing MPAs and additional newly identified priority areas). We focused on ecologically

222 and management-relevant Pelagic & Seabirds (cetaceans, seabirds, spawning areas of
223 commercially important small pelagic fish) and Benthic & Demersal features (VMEs, Habitats
224 Directive Annex I listed habitats, and EUSeaMap habitats). For each group, we conducted a
225 priority ranking described in Section 2.5, with two adjustments: (1) the analysis was restricted
226 to planning units selected for respective zones in Scenario G (all other planning units were
227 locked out), and (2) the input spatial layers and their targets were limited to the features of
228 interest.

229 **2.7. Assessing the potential impact of identified conservation priority areas on fisheries**

230 To evaluate the potential impact of restricting activities within identified priority conservation
231 areas on fisheries, we quantified the proportion of total fishing intensity overlapping with
232 priority zones in Scenario G. This scenario integrated both currently declared MPAs and newly
233 identified priority areas, enabling us to separately assess fishing intensity in each. We calculated
234 the fraction of fishing intensity within Pelagic & Seabirds (pelagic trawls, seines, and static
235 gears), Benthic & Demersal (bottom otter and beam trawls, bottom seines, and dredges), and
236 Combined (all gears) zones.

237 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

238 **3.1. Classification of the currently declared MPAs**

239 Overall, 25% of the study area was under some form of designation (Table S7, Figure 1). Spatial
240 coverage was higher in France (38% of its EEZ in the Bay of Biscay) than in Spain (12%).
241 However, management plans were in place only for 22% of the protected area, covering 5% of
242 the Bay (Figure 1).

243 There were discrepancies in the reported status of management plans between the OSPAR and
244 EEA datasets, likely due to differing update cycles. The EEA data reflected the status at the end
245 of 2023 (EEA & EC, 2025), while the more regularly updated OSPAR portal could capture
246 developments into 2025 (OSPAR, 2025). Such discrepancies, along with gaps in reporting data
247 on human activities within the EU's MPAs, have already been reported in the literature
248 (Aminian-Biquet et al., 2025).

249 Our findings provide local context for EU-wide assessments, indicating that over 80% of the
250 MPA network offers low levels of protection and allows industrial activities (Aminian-Biquet
251 et al., 2024, 2025), with many MPAs remaining non-operational due to a lack of management

252 plans (WWF, 2025). While the EU mandates such plans, their implementation in offshore
253 waters is complicated by the regionalisation process under the Common Fisheries Policy
254 (Regulation (EU) 1380/2013) which requires consensus on the conservation measures among
255 member states with fishing interests in the areas concerned, creating a regulatory bottleneck
256 that often delays or dilutes protective measures (ECA, 2020; Kingma & Walker, 2021).

257 **3.2.Spatial configurations of conservation priority areas**

258 While the overall footprint and target achievement were similar between the three-zone
259 approach (Figure 4) and reference scenarios without zone differentiation (SM2, Figures S2-S3,
260 Table S8), the three-zone approach yielded more informative solutions. For instance, some
261 planning units were selected exclusively for the Benthic & Demersal zone, highlighting areas
262 where seabed protection is needed while potentially allowing compatible pelagic activities. This
263 zonal information can be valuable for the ongoing development of MPA management plans,
264 especially given that most MPAs, both in the Bay and globally, are multi-use and permit some
265 fishing and other human activities (Burns et al., 2023), despite offering fewer conservation
266 benefits than no-take reserves (e.g., Turnbull et al., 2021). Beyond MPAs, this approach can
267 also support biodiversity-inclusive MSP by providing management-ready spatial guidance
268 across benthic and pelagic environments (UNESCO-IOC & European Commission, 2025)

269 There was a substantial overlap with existing MPAs, e.g., along the shelf break, areas in the
270 north, and off Galicia and further offshore around the Galician bank (Figure 4 A, B, E, F). This
271 convergence across multiple scenarios suggests that existing MPAs, although designated for
272 specific species or habitats (e.g., under the EU Habitats Directive), have a strong potential to
273 deliver ecosystem-wide conservation benefits, as our analysis was based on a broader scope of
274 ecosystem elements guided by EBSA criteria. Realising this potential for broader ecological
275 benefits depends on effective management.

276 This overlap may partly reflect a data availability bias, as these regions are historically data-
277 rich due to extensive surveys conducted for MPA designations. Our study incorporated a range
278 of information layers (both empirical and modelled) to mitigate this, and our results align with
279 the previous studies showing that these regions' importance for seabirds and cetaceans (Waggitt
280 et al., 2020), small pelagic fishes, tuna species, and elasmobranchs (ICES, 2021), corals
281 (Morato, González-Irusta, et al., 2020; van den Beld et al., 2017), and sponges (Gregório et al.,
282 2024). Nonetheless, results for understudied offshore deep-sea areas should be interpreted

283 cautiously due to limited data (Galparsoro et al., 2024; Lukyanova et al., 2025b), which remains
284 a challenge worldwide (Bell et al., 2025; Bridges & Howell, 2025).

285 Several areas outside existing MPAs were also consistently selected across most scenarios,
286 except C and D (Figure 4), including the southeast corner of the Bay, offshore regions north of
287 Brittany and west of Galicia. Identification of these areas supports previous research advocating
288 for their protection (Borja et al., 2022; García-Barón et al., 2019; IUCN-MMPATF, 2024b,
289 2024a; Lukyanova et al., 2025b), pointing to their high ecological value. Our results provide
290 complementary integrative evidence that could serve as a basis for considering MPA network
291 expansion.

292 Using fishing intensity as a cost layer shifted conservation priorities offshore towards areas of
293 lower fishing pressure (Figure 4 B, D, F, H). This, however, incurred ecological and spatial
294 trade-offs. The shift was most pronounced on the French continental shelf in scenarios including
295 only managed MPAs (Figure 4 B, F), resulting in 7% reduction in the number of ecological
296 targets achieved (Figure S4). Furthermore, Scenario F (ecological targets and fishing as cost)
297 required 6% more total area than its area-based equivalent, Scenario E (Figure 5).

298 This highlights a common trade-off in conservation planning, reflecting the need to balance
299 ecological and socio-economic goals (Kriegl et al., 2021). Protecting areas with lower fishing
300 pressure can reduce sectoral conflict, but care should be taken not to compromise conservation
301 objectives. A greater footprint in Scenario F indicates that the algorithm needed more space to
302 compensate for avoiding some high-productivity areas supporting abundant marine life, e.g.
303 over the French continental shelf, but also under intensive fishing (Figure S1). While a well-
304 designed MPA network can support ecosystem-based management and ultimately benefit
305 fisheries through mechanisms like spillover (Gaines et al., 2010; Grip & Blomqvist, 2020;
306 Kriegl et al., 2021), and SCP can help navigate conflicts between sectors (e.g., Boussarie et al.,
307 2023), our results underscore the immediate spatial trade-offs faced by planners.

308 **3.3. Determining high-priority areas and quantifying target achievement**

309 Areas of high relative ecological importance were concentrated along the continental shelf
310 break, north of Brittany, west of Galicia, and over the Biscay Seamount northwest of the Bay
311 (Figure 6B). The prominence of the areas with complex geomorphology and depth gradients,
312 i.e., steep shelf break incised by canyons and seamounts, aligns with their globally recognised
313 role in supporting high productivity and biodiversity (e.g., De Leo et al., 2010), as also

314 documented in the Bay (Diez et al., 2021; Sánchez et al., 2014; van den Beld et al., 2017). A
315 consistent selection of the coastal and shelf waters north of Brittany underscored their
316 ecological significance, consistent with previous research identifying it as a megafauna hotspot
317 (McClellan et al., 2014), as also highlighted in our study (Figure 7 A-B).

318 Scenarios meeting all ecological targets (E-H) consistently required greater total area (56-63%)
319 than scenarios with 30% spatial target (A-D; Figure 5). This was primarily driven by the Pelagic
320 & Seabirds zone, which constituted 29-41% of the total solution, compared to 1-6% for the
321 Benthic & Demersal and 13-26% for the Combined zone (Figure 5). In line with that, a
322 hypothetical optimised protection of 30% of the Bay was projected to meet 91% of the
323 ecological targets defined for this study, including all targets for Benthic & Demersal and 83%
324 of targets for Pelagic & Seabirds features (Figure 6A). The target shortfalls occurred for three
325 seabird species (northern fulmar (*Fulmarus glacialis*), Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus*
326 *mauretanicus*), and Manx shearwater (*Puffinus puffinus*)), seven cetaceans (fin whale
327 (*Balaenoptera physalus*), long-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala melas*), Risso's dolphin
328 (*Grampus griseus*), sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*), striped dolphin (*Stenella*
329 *coeruleoalba*), common bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*), and common dolphin
330 (*Delphinus delphis*)), and two fish species (blue shark (*Prionace glauca*) and Atlantic bluefin
331 tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*). The most significant shortfalls were among cetaceans, with fin whales
332 reaching only 34% of their target, sperm whales 38%, striped dolphins 42%, and Risso's
333 dolphins 64%. Among fishes, juveniles and adult Atlantic bluefin tuna achieved 63% and 96%
334 respectively, and juvenile blue sharks – 52%. Most of these species were associated with
335 offshore areas (Figure S5), corresponding to areas with lower overall priority ranks (Figure 6B).
336 This indicates that while critical for specific pelagic species, these offshore regions contributed
337 less to achieving the full scope of biodiversity targets defined in this study.

338 The Bay of Biscay is an important region for wide-ranging pelagic megafauna (Borja et al.,
339 2019; ICES, 2021), including as a potential reproductive area for blue sharks (Vossgaetter et
340 al., 2025). The extensive pelagic priority areas we identified align with global findings showing
341 highly mobile species use vast ocean expanses (Sequeira et al., 2025), often making exclusive
342 reliance on static MPAs both impractical and politically challenging. However, evidence
343 suggests that pelagic systems may be less resilient under exploitation than benthic ones,
344 possibly due to lower habitat complexity and species redundancy (Letessier et al., 2024),
345 highlighting the need for effective conservation strategies. Supplementing static MPAs with
346 targeted non-spatial measures (see Section 3.4) and dynamic approaches offers a promising
347 pathway (Esteban-Cantillo et al., 2025; Maxwell et al., 2015). Although implementing and

348 enforcing dynamic measures can be challenging, novel technologies – including AI, big data,
349 remote sensing, etc. – are transforming our ability to monitor and predict oceanic changes in
350 real-time, facilitating dynamic management (Bakker, 2022; Esteban-Cantillo et al., 2025).
351 Ensuring clarity and effective communication of the rules to the stakeholders remains a crucial
352 challenge, but successful examples exist (Bakker, 2022).

353 **3.4. Pinpointing priority areas for specific conservation features**

354 Cetacean priority areas were predominantly beyond the shelf break, except for the shelf area
355 north of Brittany (Figure 7A). Such a location and a vast span of high-importance areas reflect
356 their high mobility and migratory patterns. In contrast, seabirds' high-priority areas were largely
357 coastal, except over the wide continental shelf in the north (Figure 7B). Given the high mobility
358 of both groups, and seasonal presence of some species (e.g., fin whale, Balearic shearwater),
359 for their effective protection, MPAs need to be supplemented by temporal closures and non-
360 spatial measures.

361 The most pressing issue is bycatch mitigation, a major threat to both groups (Avila et al., 2018;
362 Melvin et al., 2023). A range of proven technical solutions exists, including acoustic deterrents
363 (pingers), lights, line-weighing and night-setting for longlines, and various gear modifications
364 for trawls and pots/traps (Hamilton & Baker, 2019; Lucas & Berggren, 2022; Melvin et al.,
365 2023), although their efficacy is context-dependent (Lucas & Berggren, 2022). For some cases,
366 no reliably effective technical solutions currently exist (e.g., small cetacean bycatch in trawl
367 nets, species not deterred by pingers, seabird bycatch in gillnets and purse seines; Hamilton &
368 Baker, 2019; Melvin et al., 2023). In these instances, spatial or temporal closures are often the
369 only presently viable solution to reduce mortality (Collins et al., 2021; Melvin et al., 2023).
370 Beyond bycatch, other anthropogenic threats require management. For cetaceans, vessel strikes
371 pose a serious concern; however, speed reductions and traffic separation schemes have
372 demonstrated effectiveness (Rockwood et al., 2020; Vighi, 2025). For seabirds, offshore wind
373 farms can cause displacement and must be planned precautionarily (e.g., Garthe et al., 2023).

374 Important areas for spawning of commercially important small pelagic fish were concentrated
375 on the French continental shelf and in several coastal regions, e.g., near the Gironde estuary
376 (Figure 7C). In the Bay, spring is the key spawning season for the most commercial species
377 (Borja et al., 2019). Temporal closures during this critical period can safeguard reproductive
378 individuals and enhance stock recruitment (Van Overzee & Rijnsdorp, 2015). This strategy
379 would help maintain fishery productivity while ensuring the continued viability of these species'
380 crucial role in the Bay's food web (Iglesias et al., 2025).

381 VMEs were closely associated with the shelf break (Figure 7D). Many of these areas are
382 protected under the EU Regulation 2019/1241 or fall within the existing MPAs (e.g., *Avilés*
383 *Canyon System* or recently declared *Capbreton Canyon Tributary System* MPA), highlighting
384 the need for active management of these MPAs. All important areas for Habitats Directive
385 Annex I habitats were under some form of designation and predominantly coastal, though
386 offshore MPAs like the *Galician Bank*, *Avilés Canyon System*, and *El Cachucho* were also
387 highlighted (Figure 7E). EUSeaMap habitats were distributed throughout the solution (Figure
388 7E), including areas of high importance in deep offshore areas, reflecting potential significance,
389 but also uncertainty associated with these data-poor abyssal regions of the Bay (Galparsoro et
390 al., 2024).

391 **3.5. Assessing the potential impact of identified conservation priority areas on fisheries**

392 A substantial proportion of total fishing intensity occurred within the existing MPAs (Figure
393 8). For pelagic gears (pelagic trawls and seines, static gears), 47% of fishing intensity was inside
394 MPAs, rising to 56% within the total area prioritised Scenario G. Similarly, for benthic gears
395 (bottom otter and beam trawls, bottom seines, dredges), 35% of total fishing intensity was
396 within MPAs, increasing to 43% in Scenario G.

397 MPAs with (e.g., off Brittany and the Gironde estuary) and without (e.g., large MPAs on the
398 French shelf and along the Galician coast) management plans were subject to high fishing
399 pressure (Figure 8), highlighting a need not only to finalise management plans but also to
400 strengthen protection measures. This pattern is not unique to the Bay of Biscay, as high fishing
401 pressures have been reported across the EU (Claudet et al., 2020; Dureuil et al., 2018) and NE
402 Atlantic MPAs (Roessger et al., 2022), particularly in larger MPAs (Dureuil et al., 2018).

403 Our results show the scale of potential impact on the fishing sector if harvest is restricted or
404 banned in the MPAs, revealing the political and socio-economic challenges of their
405 implementation. While MPAs may allow sustainable, non-damaging fishing methods,
406 regulations must prioritise conservation objectives (Humphreys & Clark, 2020).

407 While this study offers insight into spatial differentiation between benthic and pelagic
408 conservation priorities, further work is needed to assess the vulnerability of the ecological
409 features present across the Bay to specific fishing gears. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis
410 of trade-offs with other anthropogenic activities would also be essential. Finally, to ensure long-
411 term efficacy, spatial planning must incorporate the effects of climate change, particularly when
412 targeting dynamic features such as migratory species and oceanographic processes. This can be

413 achieved by identifying climate refugia and considering projected future species distributions
414 (Lezama-Ochoa et al., 2025; Wesselmann et al., 2024).

415 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

416 This study demonstrates how multi-zone spatial prioritisation, which systematically integrates
417 a broad scope of ecological features, can identify representative priority areas for biodiversity
418 across the benthic and pelagic environments, supporting conservation efforts and broader
419 biodiversity-inclusive MSP. However, spatial analysis is only one step in decision-making. The
420 long-term success of planning depends on integrating social, economic, and equity dimensions
421 through sustained stakeholder engagement. Our findings offer a tangible scientific basis to
422 catalyse these essential discussions.

423 Furthermore, the extensive pelagic priority areas we identified strengthen the argument that
424 static MPAs are insufficient for effective protection of biodiversity. Spatial measures should be
425 part of a broader strategy, which also includes dynamic management tools and non-spatial
426 measures like fisheries regulations and vessel strike mitigation. Implementing such complex
427 strategies is challenging and demands robust policy frameworks that enable cross-sectoral
428 coordination. Scientific assessments, such as the one presented here, provide the critical
429 evidence base to inform these frameworks and advance ecosystem-based management for the
430 long-term health of marine ecosystems in the Bay of Biscay and beyond.

431

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441 **Declaration of Interest statement**

442 The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this work.

443 **Data statement**

444 Most of the data used for this study are publicly available, except for several datasets that are
445 available from their respective sources upon request, for which the authors do not have
446 permission to share. All data sources are listed in SM1, Table B. All raster outputs from the
447 analyses presented here are published on Zenodo (Lukyanova et al., 2025a).

448 **Declaration of generative AI use**

449 During the preparation of this work, the authors used Microsoft Copilot to enhance the clarity
450 and readability of the manuscript. Copilot assisted with language refinement, grammatical
451 accuracy, and streamlining of selected sections. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and
452 edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

453 **Author Credits**

454 **O.L.:** Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Conceptualization, Methodology,
455 Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Visualization. **S.P.:**
456 Writing - Review & Editing, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision. **A.B.:** Writing -
457 Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. **I.G.:** Writing - Review & Editing, Conceptualization,
458 Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Table 1. Summary of heuristic principles for defining feature-specific conservation targets. EU Red List status categories: CR = Critically Endangered, EN = Endangered, VU = Vulnerable, NT = Near Threatened, LC = Least Concern, DD = Data deficient; VME = Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem; BoB = Bay of Biscay study area.

Category	Group of features	Heuristic principles for target-setting
Ecosystems and habitats	Known VMEs	Full protection: 100%
	VME Indicators	Known: 50% Uncertain or inferred distribution: 20%
	Benthic or coastal habitats	Certain: 75% Uncertain: 20%
	Submarine geomorphology	Seamounts: 75% Canyons: 50% Ridges, plateaus and banks: 20%
	Broad-scale classes of seabed habitats (EUSeaMap)	Occupies <= 5% of the BoB: 15% Occupies > 5%: 10% Occupies > 10%: 5% Occupies > 20% (for "seabed" class > 10%): 2%
Species	Inferred habitat suitability or density distribution	Base target: 20% + 10% per EU Red List status (NT → VU/DD → EN → CR) + 10% per occurrence in BoB (Common → Occasional → Rare)
Special importance for life-history stages of species	Breeding sites	Known: 100% Uncertain: 30%
	Foraging ranges from breeding sites	Base target: 20% If mean range > 50% of BoB: 10%
	Spawning areas	BoB is a "Very important" spawning area for a species: 50% "Important": 30% "Marginal": 10%
	Nursery/recruitment areas (inferred habitat suitability or density distribution of juveniles - commercial and conservation species)	Base target: 30% + 10% per EU Red List status (NT → VU/DD → EN → CR) + 10% per occurrence in BoB (Common → Occasional → Rare)
Biodiversity and productivity	Species / Habitats richness	Base target: 20%
	Productivity	Target for a satellite-derived estimate of productivity: 20% Target for areas of elevated productivity caused by seamounts: 75% Target for areas of elevated productivity caused by the shelf edge and canyons: 50%

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874 **Figure 1.** Map of the Bay of Biscay showing the study area, the Bay’s biogeographic limits as defined
 875 by the International Hydrographic Organisation, national Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), and the
 876 distribution of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and bottom-touching fishing gear closures for vulnerable
 877 marine ecosystems (VME closures). Protected areas are categorised by their targeted species and
 878 habitats (Pelagic & Seabirds, Benthic & Demersal, or Combined) and by the presence of a management
 879 plan (based on OSPAR and EEA Natura 2000 databases). VME closures were classified as having
 880 management plans.

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		↓ OBJECTIVE ↓			
		🛡️ 30% spatial target		👤 Ecological targets	
↓ COST LAYER ↓	Area-based	A Maximise targets in 30% area, incl. managed MPAs 🛡️ 🗺️ 🌿	C Maximise targets in 30% area, incl. all MPAs 🛡️ 🗺️ 🌿	E Min area, incl. managed MPAs, to meet all targets 👤 🗺️ 🌿	G Min area, incl. all MPAs, to meet all targets 👤 🗺️ 🌿
	Fishing intensity	B Maximise targets in 30% area, incl. managed MPAs, at min cost to fisheries 🛡️ 🚤 🌿	D Maximise targets in 30% area, incl. all MPAs, at min cost to fisheries 🛡️ 🚤 🌿	F Min area, incl. managed MPAs, to meet all targets at min cost to fisheries 👤 🚤 🌿	H Min area, incl. all MPAs, to meet all targets at min cost to fisheries 👤 🚤 🌿
		🌿 Only managed MPAs	🌿 All currently declared MPAs	🌿 Only managed MPAs	🌿 All currently declared MPAs
		↑ MPAS AS LOCKED-IN AREAS ↑			

884 **Figure 2.** Formulation of the objectives and constraints for the eight spatial conservation prioritisation
 885 scenarios. Each scenario is formulated as a combination of three parameters: (1) Objective (30% of the
 886 study area or achievement of all ecological targets defined in this study), (2) Cost layer (area-based or
 887 fishing intensity), and (3) mandatory inclusion of marine protected areas (MPAs) as locked-in areas
 888 (only MPAs with existing management plans or all currently declared MPAs).
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891 **Figure 3.** Methodological workflow for the spatial conservation prioritisation (SCP). All SCP problems
 892 were formulated as three-zone problems (Pelagic & Seabirds, Benthic & Demersal, and Combined
 893 zones), with ecological features and cost layers split into two categories (Pelagic & Seabirds, Benthic &
 894 Demersal). A given ecological feature only benefited if the planning units were allocated to the zone of
 895 its category or the Combined zone, which encompassed both categories. The costs were also incurred
 896 either in their respective zone/category, or in the Combined zone, which thus included a sum of all costs.
 897 The scenarios were run separately with area-based and with fishing intensity costs. We tested two
 898 different objectives for otherwise similarly articulated sets of SCP problems: 30% spatial target implied
 899 achieving maximum targets within 30% of the study area, and ecological targets implied reaching all
 900 targets at a minimum cost. MPAs = Marine Protected Areas.
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903 **Figure 4.** Spatial configurations of conservation priority areas in the eight considered scenarios. For scenario formulation, see Figure 2. MPAs = Marine
 904 Protected Areas, VME closures = Bottom-touching fishing gear closures for vulnerable marine ecosystems, EEZ = Exclusive Economic Zones.

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 906 **Figure 5.** Percentage of the study area identified for a conservation priority per zone in each scenario.
 907 For scenario formulation, see Figure 2. MPAs = Marine Protected Areas.
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 914 Figure 6. (A) Relationship between the spatial extent of protection and the percentage of conservation
 915 targets achieved. Target achievement increases more rapidly for Benthic & Demersal (orange) than for
 916 Pelagic & Seabird (blue) features, revealing a difference in protection efficiency. (B) Spatial distribution
 917 of high- and low-priority areas. The map identifies areas of highest ecological relevance for conservation
 918 features associated with Benthic & Demersal (orange), Pelagic & Seabird (blue), or both environments
 919 (green), with darker colours corresponding to a higher priority ranking, indicating higher importance for
 920 the respective environment. While areas were not selected in any runs. (A-B) Grey labels highlight the
 921 pelagic species with the greatest target shortfalls, and arrows indicate important areas for them. MPA =
 922 Marine protected area; VME closures = Bottom-touching fishing gear closures for vulnerable marine
 923 ecosystems; EEZ = Exclusive economic zones.
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Figure 7. Spatial prioritisation results showing relative conservation importance for specific feature groups : (A) cetaceans, (B) seabirds, (C) spawning areas of commercially important small pelagic fishes, (D) vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs), (E) Habitats Directive (HD) Annex I listed habitats, and (F) EUSeaMap broad-scale classes of seabed habitats corresponding to benthic habitat types defined by the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive. The maps identify areas of high ecological relevance per group within the priority area for its respective environment in Scenario G, with maps in the top row (A-C) representing Pelagic & Seabirds (i.e., total footprint is a combination of Pelagic & Seabirds and Combined zones) and bottom row (D-F) representing Benthic & Demersal (i.e., total footprint is a combination of Benthic & Demersal and Combined zones). MPA = Marine protected area; VME closures = Bottom-touching fishing gear closures for vulnerable marine ecosystems; EEZ = Exclusive economic zones.

933
 934 Figure 8. Fishing intensity occurring within the identified priority areas in Scenario G (aiming
 935 to meet all targets in a minimum area, including all currently declared MPAs), with (A) showing
 936 the fishing intensity by pelagic gears (pelagic trawls and seines, static gears) occurring within
 937 the Pelagic & Seabirds zone and (B) showing the fishing intensity by benthic gears (bottom
 938 otter trawls, bottom seines, dredges, beam trawls) occurring within the Benthic & Demersal
 939 zone. Among the total fishing intensity by pelagic gears, 56% occurs within the identified
 940 priority areas for the Pelagic & Seabirds zone, with 47% occurring within the currently declared
 941 Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). Among the total fishing intensity by benthic gears, 44%
 942 occurs within the identified priority areas for the Benthic & Demersal zone, with 37% occurring
 943 within the currently declared MPAs. MPA = Marine protected area; VME closures = Bottom-
 944 touching fishing gear closures for vulnerable marine ecosystems; EEZ = Exclusive economic
 945 zones.

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		↓ OBJECTIVE ↓			
		Ecological targets			
↓ COST LAYER ↓	Area-based 				
	Fishing intensity 				
		All currently declared MPAs			
↑ MPAS AS LOCKED-IN AREAS ↑					

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Conservation priority areas

Trade-off between area coverage and target achievement

Spatial distribution of high- and low-priority areas

MPAs and VME closures

- With | without management plans
- Combined (diagonal lines)
 - Pelagic & Seabirds (vertical lines)
 - Benthic & Demersal (horizontal lines)

- EEZ (orange line)
- 200 m Isobath (grey line)

Preprint not peer reviewed

Cetaceans

Seabirds

Spawning areas

VMEs

HD Annex 1 habitats

EUSeaMap habitats

Priority rank

Boundaries of the conservation priority areas

MPAs and VME closures

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Pelagic gears

Benthic and demersal gears

MPAs and VME closures

With | without management plans

- Combined
- Pelagic & Seabirds
- Benthic & Demersal

- Boundaries of the conservation priority areas
- EEZ
- 200 m Isobath

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